

From the Upward Sphere
by Brian Paul Kaess

From the upward sphere, dazzling sunbeams pass,
Such a tropical zone, one could not pretend to surpass,
The Vacas (or cows) took note of the scarcity of grass,
But that did not stop the faithful from attending Mass,
O' unending bliss! Thy bounty secured,
With the Holy Ghost's lens, this could not be obscured,
It was hard to find a shadow in this sun-bleached land,
As well as a farmer untouched by nature's hand,
But that did not stop the cartel from making their demand,
And only justice was left with her reprimand,
In the state of Durango, the cloud forest was made up of pines, oaks, & firs,
Here Nature's splendor revealed no slurs,
In June the lightning flashes came,
Gazing towards the heavens made one want to proclaim,
The lake at La Victoria looked like God's Country most sublime,
To the summit of Mt. Ramos did Mayte invite me to climb,
A mere mo-hill at best, much 'Ganas' it did not require,
But after reaching the top, I felt no shortage of desire,
However upon the descent was where the true test came,
When I tripped over a pipe, and had no else to blame,
My leg felt like a pretzel stinging with pain,
But I straightened up, started walking, and my effort was not in vain,
The Raven perched upon the old church fence, some came forward at their own expense,
The Devil was certain to dispense, a round of Jack Daniels in glasses most immense,
May the Blackbird sing her tune beneath the Northern Star, as I gaze upon her from afar,
In other empyreal realms had I sought, but found their spiritual treasure nought,
Though I never met the Christian Czar, Jesus made sure that was no bar,
With blazoned script did I pen, tender breezes that caress,
The Norman conquest did the Irish withstand,
But in Tenochtitlan, the Spanish played their hand,
May the ancient bard rejoice once more and touch upon Mexico's forlorn shore.